

Sydney Startups Ecosystem

Report by coursework students of UTS 94663 Navigating Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and Initiating Change, 2022 cohort

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Foreword

This report is part of a series of student-generated series about entrepreneurial ecosystems. Each report is a derivative of their coursework. The subject, 94663 Navigating Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and Initiating Change, is a core subject in the Diploma in Innovation at TD School and a popular elective across other UTS degree programs. The subject was piloted as part of the launch for the Sydney School of Entrepreneurship in 2017¹ and draws on prior research and engagement projects to visualise entrepreneurial ecosystems.²

The subject runs for three weeks in July, during which teams of students are tasked with defining and exploring an entrepreneurial ecosystem, understanding its history and visualising its current state. Based on that knowledge, they then develop proposals to advance the ecosystem.

The reports reflect the work that was presented publicly to invited guests and stakeholders in the subject, as well as members of the public who joined the presentations via the publicly available event page.

General Methodology

In partnership with Investment NSW (e.g., Sydney Startup Hub) and Spark Festival, the cohort of ~45 students was given the option to focus on Sydney CBD, Western Sydney, or Nationally. Additionally, one team was based overseas and was free to choose an international city to navigate.

The general method of this study follows our own method of evaluating ecosystems that has evolved over years of experience, in consultation with an Australian wide network of ecosystem researchers. While our process is not yet well documented, it is entirely consistent with the 2018 guide produced by the German Society for International Collaboration,³ promoted by the Aspen Network of Development Entrepreneurs (ANDE).

In addition to learning about ecosystems, teams engaged with ecosystems in authentic and immersive learning experiences. Stakeholder types and specific stakeholders in the ecosystem were identified based on Stam's seminal (2015) review of ecosystem factors. Insights about the ecosystem were generated by analysing desktop reports and media interviews involved those stakeholders. Where possible, teams conducted their own interviews of key stakeholders, including asking them about the ecosystem's history, evolution and critical events, and their vision for how it may evolve further. By synthesising such reports and interviews from multiple stakeholders, teams developed a composite story of the ecosystem's evolution, visualised its current state and identified specific opportunities for change. These reports present this analysis of the ecosystems' evolution as well as the team's proposal for specific interventions by which to intentionally advance the ecosystem in a specific direction.

The method can be tailored to specific ecosystems, ranging from rural communities through to internationally acclaimed innovation precincts. The breadth of Stam's framework and this method enables pushing back against the myth that innovation and entrepreneurship is primarily the domain of high-tech startups and VCs. While they do play a very important role, they are not the only organisations that matter to create economic growth (Brown & Mason, 2017; Spigel et al., 2020).

Field research for coursework follows the same principles as field research for academic purposes. As a result, the students' work mirrored the process of ecosystem research conducted by Martin Bliemel, for which he has ethics approval (HREC# ETH18-3020).

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¹ Bliemel, M., Schweitzer, J., Roy, G., Keitel, A., Nicolas, L., Miles, M., ... & Griffith, S. (2019, November). Herding cats to co-create cross-university courses in record time. *UIIN University-Industry Interaction Conference 2019*. University Industry Innovation Network.

² Bliemel, M. (2019). University-based entrepreneurial ecosystems and their visualisations. *University-Industry Innovation Magazine*.

³ <https://www.goethe.de/resources/files/pdf197/5.-guide-for-mapping-the-entrepreneurial-ecosystem.pdf>

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1 Evolution of the Ecosystem

1.1 Introduction

Freeman & Engel (2007) state that entrepreneurs that develop firms based on significant inventions fall into a societal role known as the "professional entrepreneur." With a broad economy and a stable, low-risk business environment, the NSW government established the Sydney Startup Hub to assist, develop, and strengthen the startup ecosystem. However, it motivates and encourages diversity in the NSW startup community. Sydney Startups focuses on ecosystems because ecosystems give startups networking opportunities, allowing entrepreneurs to prioritise their goals (Innovation Depot, 2021).

1.2 Stakeholders

The Sydney Startup Ecosystem has rapidly grown thanks to its stakeholders' leadership and incubators. Among the most critical stakeholders in accelerating the growth of the startup ecosystem is the Sydney Startup Hub, built through the strong support of the government represented by NSW Premier Gladys Berejiklian and a \$35 million investment. This construction makes the Sydney Startup Hub the first innovation hub of its kind in Australia (James, 2017). Vithoulkas is also a stakeholder, a city councillor and prominent small business owner in the city, and the founder of a tech startup herself, Eagle Waves Radio, a digital radio platform for small businesses. Her influence is helpful to the startup community because it means a deeper understanding of the ecosystem beyond those who work for the city information (Startup Daily, 2015).

Sydney Startup Hub tenants include startups, established organizations, a range of industry sectors, and the for-profit and not-for-profit sectors (NSW, 2022). Also, the incubators and co-working spaces in the Sydney Startups Ecosystem such as Fishburners, Tank Stream Labs, BlueChilli, WeCo, iCentral, Gravity, ATP Innovations, The Hub Sydney, The Emporium, muru-D, Jumpstart, Springboard, Startmate and INCUBATE, among others (Startup Daily, 2015). Also, TSL was founded in 2012, and it is one of the stakeholders in Sydney Startups. CEO Bradley Delamare leads Tank Stream Labs. TSL is one of Australia's largest technology-focused startup incubators and co-locations, and Bradley works with startups such as Optus, Survey Monkey and Airtasker. He helps them solve problems and understand management risks (not specified, 2022).

1.3 Education

The Sydney Start-ups Ecosystem Canvas seeks to provide local entrepreneurs with a complete list of resources for each stage of their start-up journey and to provide communities with an essential structure for mapping their ecosystems (Founder Institute, 2018). In 2016, the school received \$25 million from the government of New South Wales to fund university operations (USYD, 2017). However, the Sydney Start-ups Ecosystem has partnered with other institutions, such as TAFE, UNSW, USYD, and UTS, to provide education relevant to the ecosystem start-ups for those who have launched a start-up or wish to hone their entrepreneurial skills and mindset (Ward, 2017). The government of New South Wales established a community for innovators and entrepreneurs to share, learn, build networks, and bring their ideas to reality, thereby contributing to a more sustainable and eco-friendly global community.

1.4 Financial

Finance in the Sydney startup ecosystem is skyrocketing due to having many stakeholders. According to Startup Genome's report, the Sydney ecosystem is now worth \$24 billion (Simon, 2021). Accelerating the financial development of the Sydney startup ecosystem is mainly because of the Sydney Startup Hub. The main factors driving its development are Local Communities, Government, Sponsors, and Investors. Since 2018, the Sydney Startup Hub has created nearly 6,000 jobs. It strengthens Sydney's position as a startup hub by attracting investors, supporting the startup community, and accelerating the development of the Sydney startup ecosystem (NSW Investment, 2019). To further accelerate the growth of the Sydney startup ecosystem, the NSW Government has invested \$35 million in the Sydney Startup Hub to attract more investors and sponsors (Rohan, 2017). This investment also makes the Sydney Entrepreneurship Hub the largest entrepreneurial centre in the southern hemisphere.

1.5 Infrastructure

Infrastructure is the foundation for keeping businesses operating and improving, and it also aids in the ecosystem development for start-ups. Two key components of the infrastructure are the planning and the start-up hub. The physical systems within infrastructure are typically capital-intensive and high-cost investments important to a region or country's economic development and ecosystems (Michael, 2022). In planning, EPM project management consulting is the key to pushing the development of the Sydney start-ups ecosystem. EPM is a medium-sized consulting firm founded over 20 years ago and is one of Australia's top companies for professional services in the building and real estate industries (Boyle, 2022). In the fields of development management, town planning, construction project management, building consulting, and facilities management, they have more than 100 years of combined expertise. In 2017 EPM are helping the infrastructure in Sydney's start-up community to develop strategy, plans, and budgets and carry out initiatives that will produce high-performance outcomes (Chair's Foreword; not specified, 2022). This result push strengthens Sydney's start-up ecosystem.

2 Ecosystem Mapping

The entrepreneurial ecosystem is similar to a brainstorming session for our ideas. It must analyse the ideas and how they connect to one another, as well as how they have multiple relationships with our ideas. This is why we are concentrating on ecosystem mapping.

Figure 1: Sydney Startups Ecosystem Map

Ecosystem mapping can also be used to visualise your company's products and the surrounding systems, processes, and data flows. By mapping an organisation's ecosystem, it is possible to obtain a comprehensive view of all key stakeholders, Education, Infrastructure, and Financial. Those key

components are linked to interacting with key stakeholders and raising awareness. Such as Education's efforts to recruit additional institutions into the ecosystem. The financial department is searching for investors or sponsors for the startups. However, the map also satisfies infrastructure requirements by collaborating with EMP project management and having more accelerator startups.

2.1 Current Ecosystem Mapping

According to UTS Institute for Sustainable Futures (2017), The Acceleration Program offers assistance in the form of mentoring, business coaching, and access to investor and industry leader networks. To accelerate each startup's development and increase their likelihood of success in providing energy resources to the ecosystem in the real world. In addition, the NSW Government supported jobs in the state by awarding the EnergyLab a grant of \$120,000 to help develop Australia's first start-up accelerator programme aimed at bolstering the state's renewable and advanced energy sector (NSW Industry, 2017). For instance, EnergyLab and UTS have collaborated to develop a start-up accelerator programme for UTS students. Because of the rapid development of Sydney's entrepreneurial centre, it has attracted many investors and shareholders. Therefore, it has also accelerated the development of Sydney's entrepreneurial ecosystem finance in disguise. Many investors believe this measure in New South Wales has promoted finance growth and reversed Sydney's position and trend in the global entrepreneurial finance market (James, 2017).

In this ecosystem, the Stone & Chalk fintech hub and TSL as tenants of the new facility foster collaboration and connectivity within the local start-up and bring the ecosystem to more regions (James, 2017). According to Startup Genome (2020), this move gives the Sydney start-up ecosystem an international perspective, which significantly boosts the Sydney start-up ecosystem's financial market. Furthermore, there are many infrastructures startup hubs such as Sydney Startup Hub, Tank Streams Lab, Scaleup Hub, and Tech central. These four primary centres, which also boost the city's status as a hub for Sydney's entrepreneur's start-up-up ecosystem, are the driving forces behind the expansion of the Sydney start-up-up ecosystem. The Tank Streams Lab is one of them as well as a technological supporter and participant in the Sydney start-up ecosystem. The entrepreneurial ecosystem has six main areas: strategy, finance, culture, support, human capital and marketing. All domains shift from traditional economic thinking to an innovative perspective (Stam, 2019). The Sydney Startup Ecosystem is a network of accelerators and incubators, such as TSL and Fishburners, that provide startups with expertise and early-stage funding to implement their business models rapidly. Establishing more startups and strong government support and management will enable Sydney tech startups to proliferate. This will create more jobs and boost the local culture and economy.

3 Leverage Proposal

3.1 Vision of the state of EE in the next 10 years

The Sydney Startup Hub is expected to significantly expand the Sydney start-up ecosystem over the next ten years. Other accelerators, incubators, co-working spaces, and start-up events are furthering the technology's reach. Our research revealed that in the future, there is a need to strengthen the partnership between the Sydney Startup Hub and other universities to attract and retain more talent for start-ups. We also discovered that Tank Stream Labs is an accelerator start-up in Sydney Startup Hub, and TSL has entered the Scaleup Hub in Tech Central. TSL is committed to assisting emerging and existing start-ups and scale-ups to maintain its position as the leading home for innovation in the Australian tech ecosystem.

We have interviewed Dean McEvoy. He is a former student of UTS student. Currently, Dean is a start-up investor, technology advisor and founder. Dean McEvoy is also a co-founder and CEO of Spreets, and he has made over \$100 million in tech investments (including four unicorns: Canva, Zoon, Safety Culture, and Culture Amp) through direct investment, Startmate, and as a limited partner at Blackbird Ventures. However, the primary reason for interviewing Dean McEvoy is to learn about the start-up's ecosystem vision for the next ten years. He also mentions that the Sydney Startup Hub works to encourage startups to share their visions for Sydney's next ten years, such as how to be a top environmental performer, achieve design excellence, and promote sustainable growth. A modernised, innovative economy is also a transformed and innovative economy. However, he claims that achieving net-zero emissions by 2035 is the project's main objective. Additionally, he believes this approach will strengthen the economy in the next ten years. In this case, Sydney Startup Hub is focusing on attaining net zero-emission in the next ten years, as predicted in the interview. Many start-ups must focus on sustainability because it is critical for a better future for business, activities, and survival.

Throughout what we have interviewed via email Daniel Wasilewsky, Head of Business Development and Digital of Tank Stream Labs, he is also a former student from UTS. He has been the founder of FreeGuides from 2018 until now. He is focusing on his new company more than Tank Stream Labs. However, he still works at TSL and does his position. Moreover, we discovered that TSL (Tank Stream Labs) has worked with hundreds of successful technology start-ups over the last ten years since 2012. He also mentioned that there had been numerous instances in Tank Stream Labs where a simple conversation has led to new opportunities for many businesses and individuals. Currently, TSL has a distinctive style that emphasises how collaboration, community, and innovation serve as the foundations of business expansion. Also, he states that "We maintain these links as we expand as a company through 2022 and beyond". This emphasises that TSL's goal is to innovate technology in their co-working spaces and give new opportunities for start-ups in the future while also seeking to keep them connected. TSL also intends to expand the start-up significantly and strengthen the EE economy.

3.2 Lever 1: Sydney Startup Hub finding institution to join community

Who:

This report surfaces through an interview with Dean McEvoy that the first lever for the success of the Sydney Startup Hub has been built through government incentives and support. On behalf of her government, one of the critical stakeholders, NSW Premier Gladys Berejiklian, invested \$35 million in the fourth quarter of 2017 to support the Sydney Startup Hub. 40% of the nation's startups established their companies in NSW in 2017, and this investment will attract more startups to set up head offices in NSW (Reporter, 2017). Meanwhile, the NSW government has said in its 2017-2018 budget that it will allocate around \$2.2 billion in skills training and business-related programs to help startups. And Jobs for NSW has also given \$10 million to support the development of a network of incubators. It has also directly invested \$3 million between 2016 and 2017 to fund startups (Bindi, 2017).

How:

NSW has a website called Sydney Startup Hub - Investment NSW, which provides a platform for entrepreneurs and founders to share their knowledge, experiences and how to network to bring these ideas to life. The government website also supports the NSW entrepreneurial ecosystem making the state

the most effective entrepreneurial region to drive employment opportunities (Investment NSW, 2022). An initiative launched by the NSW Government on January 1, 2017, is called the Business Connect program (Bindi, 2017). This program focuses on helping and assisting in setting up new businesses and supporting startups. The government will organize lectures and seminars. The focus is to provide professional services and established incubators such as Fishburners, Stone & Chalk, and Tank Stream Labs. However, Incubators that partner with universities can allow students to learn about the role of starting their incubators. It also acts as an advocate (Australian Institute, 2019). And they will provide professional guidance, knowledge, and space for startups. Enables startups to find their company's business value and goals to build their business model. The proposed lever for the future of the Sydney Startup Hub to improve environmental issues is the NSW government's incentive to incubators to help more startups build their ecosystems to try to decarbonize to net zero (NSW, 2022). For example, climate startups are scaling up at the Sydney Startup Hub. Climate technology is a rapidly growing field, from developing clean energy technologies at the outset to manufacturing building materials that reduce building consumption. The Greenhouse will specialize in developing technology solutions and startups that benefit the environment. A 10-year rent subsidy from the NSW government will help Greenhouse support and develop emerging climate technologies. It will also make its technology available to other startups working towards net-zero (City of Sydney, 2022).

When:

In an interview with Dean McEvoy, He told us there is a talent shortage in the Sydney entrepreneurial industry. The government's support and investment in incubation development will help attract more talent in the future and improve the ecological issues in NSW. Sydney Startup Hub must implement incentives through NSW Premier's stakeholders and incubators to achieve the above goals. However, the NSW government can offer scholarships and competitions for degrees such as University Entrepreneurship Honours. These awards and competitors will help develop more talent. An incubator, such as Fishburners, signed a three-year partnership with UTS, thus helping to bring UTS undergraduates into the entrepreneurial ecosystem (Costa, 2018). However, suppose UTS startups and interns are interested in Fishburners coworking space. In that case, they will provide UTS startups and interns with their office space, they will also offer honours, and those selected will receive business advice from Fishburners, such as legal, accounting and marketing. Also, they provide expert workshops and troubleshooting sessions. Moreover, there is also Tank Stream Labs, which has partnered with Australiance for startup internships, which not only provides university students with internships at startups to familiarize themselves with the learning environment but also the opportunity to become regular employees in the future. It also provides talent for startups (Simon, 2021). According to the Australiance (2022), Tank Stream Labs will offer college students a six-month internship to become a permanent employees. Therefore, Australiance's talent has assisted over 200 graduates from Australia, the United States, and Asia from leading colleges in providing professional experience in Australia. Therefore, this is an opportunity for young talent to establish their startups, and it benefits the Sydney Startup Hub by bringing in more people to support the creation of a sustainable environment. Younger people are more environmentally conscious than previous generations of elders and will be better able to provide innovation that will help achieve net zero in the future.

3.3 Lever 2: Sydney Startup Hub Accelerator Tank Stream Labs Entering Scaleup Hub

Who

In order for the startup ecosystem to expand, many changes must be made to facilitate a more diverse industry in terms of investment and innovative idea generation. The majority of startups require financial investment to shift from a startup to a scaled and operational firm, with MVPs producing commercially viable products and processes (Harnish, 2020). A few things should be changed so that the startup ecosystem may grow and the sector can become more diverse. Through interviews, Daniel Wasilewsky has mentioned that Tank Stream Labs mainly focused on the technological platform. This is a digital age, and if a startup is to thrive in it, it must provide appropriate protection for the platforms and networks on which it operates (Creately, 2021). Moreover, Tank Stream Labs is one of the Sydney Startup Hub accelerators, startups aimed at accelerating renewable energy technology innovation. TSL has just entered the scale-up Hub in Tech Central to innovate business in digital and emerging technology scale-ups in order to extend their co-working spaces (Thomsen, 2022).

How & When

These days Global warming, pollution, ecological decline, and loss of natural resources are all potential causes for concern in the present environmental situation. Scaleup hub use accelerators to help their

startup companies overgrown, and having more Scaleups can help have a good influence on the environment and help reduce Australia's carbon emissions. Start-up enterprises will connect with startup accelerators or incubators to gain an advantage in the Australian market. Baldassarre G (2017) reports that the government invests \$35 million in Sydney Startup Hub to shore up the technology. In startup accelerators, certain innovative businesses may locate corresponding mentors who can assist them in expanding their understanding of entrepreneurship through their training programmes (Aditya, 2022). However, Tank Stream Labs are entering the Scaleup Hub in Tech Central because TSL wants to expand the co-working spaces for technology-related new startups and breeding ground for entrepreneurs, specialised industry leaders and scale-ups. This reason could boost the NSW economy and connect with other entrepreneurs in the ecosystem. For specific stakeholders, the reward of this technology is that they will gain and experience the possible benefits and opportunities of this technology as well as some opportunities in the ecosystem (Leonard-Barton & A. Kraus, 2014). As a result, more successful startups are utilising and developing technologies to assist the ecosystem. Technology has brought many new intelligent, seasoned, and business trained members to the Sydney startup ecosystem.

In the current environment, startups have access to a wealth of resources. As a result, the programme will inform and direct new businesses as they develop and seek out appropriate possibilities. The technology will aid startup business owners in developing and identifying opportunities based on the entrepreneurial hub in the ecosystem (Mason & Brown, 2014). Tank Stream Labs will cover the "how" and "why" of studying business in the course. Some successful founders share their knowledge to aid startup enterprises in expanding more quickly. According to Startup Daily, Thomsen (2022) states that as TSL's technology-centric site, the scale-up hub has a workspace of 4,000 square meters and currently has more than 200 technology companies. They intend to launch additional new enterprises in covid-19, anticipating a surge in demand. Tank Stream labs primarily focus on scale-up in Tech Central by emphasising carbon emission-reducing on technological platforms. In our interview with Daniel Wasilewsky, Tank Stream Labs has worked with hundreds of successful entrepreneurs over the last ten years. It also creates chances and aids many entrepreneurs. In terms of technology, it assists startup entrepreneurs in overcoming relevant obstacles in order to establish the groundwork for corporate development.

3.4 Value of the proposed levers

Lever 1

The reason for Leveraging Option one in this report is to enable the start-up ecosystem to protect the environment and bring more talent to the Sydney Startup Hub. The value of incubation providing technology to other start-ups is to work together towards the goal of net-zero. The Sydney Startup Hub also partners with universities to offer internships for graduates. This allows young talent from universities to gain experience with start-ups at the university to learn more about the start-up ecosystem and to better integrate into the ecosystem of their start-ups in the future. Also, they try to bring more talent to the Sydney Startup Hub. However, accelerator incubators start-ups collaborate with other institutions to attract talented start-ups into their co-working spaces, such as Fishbuners, and Tank Stream Labs. Therefore, the proposed leverage will not only benefit the development of Sydney's start-up hub and ecosystem but also provide more job opportunities and innovation for young start-up talent in NSW.

Lever 2

The last lever of the leverage proposal tends to be the most crucial part. Achieving into the Scaleup Hub in Tech Central is one of the significant opportunities to rub shoulders with order Tech Central residents such as Atlassian, Commonwealth Bank, and more. These advantages and opportunities show the Tank Stream Labs start-up to the international scaleup. Moreover, Tank Stream Labs is mainly focused on technology. The technology will aid the start-up business owners in developing and identifying possibilities based on the entrepreneurial hub in the ecosystem. The fundamental goal of this strategy is that Tank Stream Labs are trying to show the world that the start-ups are accelerating their start-ups by providing co-working spaces for technology related to new young start-ups. Also, TSL has a distinctive style that emphasis how collaboration, community, and innovation serve as the foundations of business expansion such as Scaleup Hub. Tank Stream Lab joins the Scale Hub because they want to expand the breeding ground for entrepreneurs, specialized industry leaders, and scale-ups.

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